

Green Banking Practices and Customer Behaviour: Evidence from Mauritius

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Abstract. Green banking (GB) has been introduced as a solution to minimize the carbon emissions associated with banking activities by encouraging paperless financial services through the extensive application of technology. This study aims to analyse the impact of GB practices on customer behaviours and has adopted a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design targeting bank customers in Mauritius. The study found that GB practices significantly influence customers' perceptions; specifically, GB is positively associated with customers' behaviours particularly, customer trust, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. This research therefore sheds some new insights on the adoption of GB as a customer management strategy by banking institutions.

Keywords: Green Banking, Customer Trust, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty.

1 Introduction

Green banking (GB) started to gain momentum in the early 2000s as banks and financial institutions acknowledged the significance of sustainability in light of increasing environmental issues. The word "green" in GB relates to a bank's environmental responsibility and operational efficiency (Nisha *et al.*, 2020). This concept was developed to integrate environmental accountability into the banking sector, focusing on reducing the ecological impact of banking activities (Babiak and Trendafilova, 2011). The initial initiatives concentrated on cutting down on paper usage, promoting digital banking, and encouraging online banking and e-statements (Iqbal *et al.*, 2018). As the awareness of climate change increased and regulatory pressures grew, the banking sector began adopting green practices such as constructing energy-efficient buildings, establishing solar-powered branches, and utilizing environmentally friendly technologies.

In today's digital landscape, consumers demand cashless transactions and 24/7 access to electronic banking services, which is why GB provides solutions such as e-cards, online banking, and ATMs (Shampa and Jobaid, 2017). In response to climate change, customers are increasingly drawn to banks that focus on energy conservation. To fulfill these expectations, banks are implementing eco-friendly infrastructure, utilizing energy-efficient devices, and building green structures that reduce resource usage and environmental effects (IDRBT, 2021). Banks are also embracing sustainable

practices to boost energy efficiency and make better use of resources, such as establishing solar-powered branches, eco-friendly ATMs, and low-energy equipment. These initiatives not only help to lower carbon footprints but also strengthen the banks' commitment to sustainability, highlighting their dedication to eco-friendly initiatives (Saharwal, 2022).

The financial services sector is a crucial part of Mauritius' economy, accounting for 13.1% of the GDP, with banking and capital markets contributing 6.6% alone (Economic Development Board, 2023). Therefore, since banks and financial institutions play a vital role in the economy of Mauritius, it is essential for them to adopt green practices, thereby fostering a green and sustainable economy, which necessitates regulatory measures. As part of its 2020/2021 financial plan, the Mauritian Government intended to create a framework for green finance, which includes supervisory and regulatory systems to facilitate the issuance of "sustainable and green bonds." This initiative is in accordance with the country's obligations under the Paris Agreement and the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for "Sustainable Development" (Blumenthal *et al.*, 2022). To support this goal, the Bank of Mauritius (BOM) issued guidelines for sustainable bonds in June 2021, while the Financial Services Commission (FSC) released and subsequently revised guidelines for the issuance of "Corporate and Green Bonds" from December 2021 to April 2022 (Blumenthal *et al.*, 2022). In 2025, the BOM initiated the Sustainable Use of Natural Resources and Energy Finance (SUNREF) program to incorporate climate risk into financial regulation, enhance analytical capabilities, fill climate data gaps, and strengthen the Climate Change Centre (Bank of Mauritius, 2025). Nonetheless, Mauritius still does not possess a thorough legal framework specifically aimed at GB.

Sharma and Choubey (2022) pointed out the relatively limited research in the GB domain. Although some research has indicated that green initiatives may enhance customer trust, satisfaction, and loyalty (Smith *et al.*, 2021), the precise connection between these behaviours and GB is still not well understood (Aslam and Jawaid, 2023). In Mauritius, GB is still a relatively novel concept, and there is a scarcity of guidelines, regulatory structures, and policies pertaining to green financing. Additionally, Mauritian law has yet to clarify the term "green," which could result in problems such as greenwashing. This poses a challenge as Mauritius is at the beginning phase of adopting green initiatives within its financial services sector, and its judicial system has not yet addressed such matters (Blumenthal *et al.*, 2022). Consequently, by examining the effect of GB on customer behaviours particularly trust, satisfaction, and loyalty; this research aims to fill a critical gap in the literature especially in Mauritius where GB is still at its infancy stage. The study therefore attempted to answer the following research question: What is the association between Green Banking practices and customer behaviours, particularly in terms of trust, satisfaction, and loyalty?

As sustainability becomes increasingly vital to consumers, comprehending how GB can affect customer trust, satisfaction, and loyalty is crucial for banks looking to attract and retain an environmentally conscious customer base (Nouri and Jafari, 2021). This research aims to enrich the understanding of GB by demonstrating that adherence to eco-friendly principles and showcasing environmental accountability can improve not only social and ecological results but also customers' equity for banks. It shows that

when banks operate ethically, consumers tend to place greater trust in and feel more satisfied with their green products and services.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: section two provides a comprehensive review of the existing literature, with particular emphasis on the various customer behaviours associated with GB. The following section then outlines the methodological approach adopted in this study, detailing the research design and data collection methods. Section four then presents the findings in line with extant literature and the last section concludes the paper by summarizing the main insights and offering practical recommendations.

2 Overview of Literature

2.1 Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder Theory posits that organizations are influenced by various stakeholders who can affect corporate decisions and performance (Amran *et al.*, 2015). This perspective gained prominence when the Business Roundtable (2019) expanded corporate responsibility beyond shareholders to include broader stakeholder and environmental concerns (Harrison *et al.*, 2020). The banking sector is central to sustainability debates due to its alignment with global initiatives such as the Paris Agreement and the Sustainable Development Goals (Chen *et al.*, 2022). Banks engage with multiple internal and external stakeholders, including customers, employees, regulators, government, media, and the environment (Sarro *et al.*, 2007; Ruiz *et al.*, 2009). These stakeholders significantly influence the adoption of GB practices, particularly in developing economies (Prerana and Arup, 2022). This study adopts Stakeholder Theory with a specific focus on customers, who are critical stakeholders in banking institutions (Tang *et al.*, 2013). Failure to meet customers' expectations regarding green practices may result in reduced banking engagement and usage (Choudhury *et al.*, 2013).

2.2 Green Behaviour

There is a growing tendency for people to demonstrate green behaviour today. Consumers who are more concerned about environmental protection are increasingly inclined to purchase green products, which helps promote sustainable behaviours (Kirmani and Khan, 2016). The decision to buy green products is influenced by an individual's attitude toward the environment and its preservation. Several studies have found a strong positive relationship between customer satisfaction and purchase intention (Reshmi and Johnson, 2014). When customers are satisfied with a product's sustainability, they are more likely to buy it. This satisfaction, gained through purchasing and using green products, fosters trust and loyalty which ultimately encourages repeat purchases.

2.3. Green Banking and Customer Behaviours

2.3.1. Customer Trust

Customer trust in green contexts reflects consumers' belief in a firm's genuine commitment to environmental responsibility (Chen, 2013; Hameed *et al.*, 2021). Prior studies show that environmentally friendly banking practices—such as paperless transactions and energy-efficient technologies—enhance perceptions of professionalism and reliability, thereby strengthening trust (Hameed *et al.*, 2021; Malik and Singh, 2022). Empirical evidence from South Korea indicates that transparent communication of green initiatives positively influences customer trust (Lee *et al.*, 2019). Similarly, alignment between customers' environmental values and bank practices has been shown to increase trust (Tzeng and Chang, 2019). However, perceptions of greenwashing negatively affect trust, as demonstrated by Chen (2020) in Taiwan. These mixed findings indicate an unresolved relationship between GB and customer trust. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H₀: Green Banking has no association with Customer Trust.

H₁: Green Banking has a significant association with Customer Trust.

2.3.2. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction refers to the pleasure derived when services meet or exceed expectations (Suhartanto *et al.*, 2020). Studies suggest that customers perceive environmentally responsible banks as offering higher service quality, leading to greater satisfaction (Ibe-enwo *et al.*, 2019; Pawar and Munuswamy, 2022). Transparency in environmental policies further enhances satisfaction by fostering a sense of connection and value among customers (Dangelico and Vocalelli, 2017; Shabir *et al.*, 2023). Survey-based research in India identified a positive relationship between GB initiatives and customer satisfaction (Nair and Gopakumar, 2017). Conversely, Ahmed and Razzaq (2017) found a weak relationship in Pakistan, attributing dissatisfaction to doubts about the authenticity of green initiatives and the absence of financial incentives. Given these inconsistent findings, the following hypotheses are formulated:

H₀: Green Banking has no association with Customer Satisfaction.

H₂: Green Banking has a significant association with Customer Satisfaction.

2.3.3. Customer Loyalty

Several studies report a positive association between GB practices and customer loyalty in the banking sector (Julia and Kassim, 2020). Customers often favour banks with sustainable offerings, such as green mortgages and eco-friendly financial products (Lee and Chang, 2019). Empirical evidence from North Cyprus confirms a direct positive impact of GB on customer loyalty (Ibe-enwo *et al.*, 2019), as environmentally conscious customers tend to remain engaged with such banks (Mansoor and Hossain, 2022). Additionally, GB initiatives contribute to a favourable green reputation, which

reinforces loyalty (Herath and Herath, 2019; Sharma and Choubey, 2022). However, Tiwari and Sharma (2019) reported limited effects of GB on loyalty, noting that many customers did not prioritize environmental initiatives when selecting banks. These mixed results highlight a gap in the literature, particularly within developing countries such as Mauritius. Accordingly, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H₀: Green Banking has no association with Customer Loyalty.

H₃: Green Banking has a significant association with Customer Loyalty.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design and Sampling

This study adopted a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design to examine the impact of GB practices on customer trust, satisfaction, and loyalty in Mauritius. The target population comprised bank customers aged 18 years and above, with at least secondary-level education and a basic awareness of GB practices. Given the impracticality of surveying all bank account holders in Mauritius, the study relied on an estimated adult banking population of 940,300 as of June 2025. Using a 5% margin of error, the minimum sample size was determined to be 385 respondents. A total of 382 questionnaires were collected; after excluding incomplete and inconsistent responses, 376 valid questionnaires were retained for analysis. A purposive, non-probability sampling technique was employed to ensure that respondents possessed sufficient exposure to or awareness of GB practices. Participants were drawn from environments associated with financial and sustainability awareness, including employees in commercial banks, offshore companies, insurance firms, credit unions, and regulatory bodies. University students and academic staff in business, finance, economics, and environmental studies were also included. In addition, customers from various banking institutions in Mauritius formed part of the sample to enhance diversity in banking experiences. The sampling methodology represents a primary constraint on the study's generalizability. By employing purposive non-probability sampling, the research inadvertently focused on individuals with finance-related or sustainability-aware backgrounds. While these respondents provide deep insight into specialized banking sectors, their perspectives likely suffer from selection bias. Their high level of literacy in ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) topics does not reflect the average Mauritian bank customer.

3.2 Instrument Development and Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed based on established constructs identified in the literature. The questionnaire consisted of two sections: demographic information and measurement items. The demographic section captured respondents' gender, age, education level, occupation, and income. The measurement section comprised 21 items assessing GB awareness, green practices, customer trust, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty. All measurement items were adapted from validated scales in prior studies. Specifically, GB awareness was measured using four items adapted from Shibli and Mollah (2015); green practices were assessed using eight

items drawn from Moise *et al.* (2021) and Hameed *et al.* (2021); customer trust was measured using three items adapted from Chen (2013), Martínez (2015), Issock *et al.* (2020), and Pahlevi and Suhartanto (2020); customer satisfaction was measured using three items from Han *et al.* (2018), Issock *et al.* (2020), and Pahlevi and Suhartanto (2020); and customer loyalty was assessed using three items adapted from Issock *et al.* (2020) and Pahlevi and Suhartanto (2020). All items were measured using a Likert-scale format. The questionnaire was administered primarily through an online Google Form, with the survey link distributed via social media platforms including WhatsApp, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Facebook. This approach facilitated wider reach and encouraged snowball sampling, whereby respondents shared the survey link within their networks. To complement online data collection, a limited number of printed questionnaires were also distributed to bank customers in selected locations.

3.3 Instrument Reliability

Content validity was ensured by adapting measurement items from well-established prior studies and aligning them with the study objectives. The questionnaire was designed to directly capture perceptions related to GB awareness, practices, and customer behavioural outcomes. Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficients computed via SPSS version 21. The results indicated high internal consistency across all constructs, with Cronbach's alpha values exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.70. As shown in Table 1, all scales demonstrated excellent reliability, confirming the consistency and robustness of the measurement instruments.

Table 1: Reliability of constructs

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Items
Green Banking Awareness	0.931	4
Green Practices	0.969	8
Customer Behaviours (Trust, Satisfaction, Loyalty)	0.987	9

3.4 Data analysis procedures

To examine associations between constructs measured on ordinal scales or that do not meet the assumptions of normal distribution, this study uses Spearman's rank-order correlation coefficient. Spearman's correlation is a non-parametric measure of association that assesses the strength and direction of a monotonic relationship between ranked variables. This approach does not assume linearity or normal distribution, making it appropriate for Likert-type survey data and ordinal measures commonly used in behavioural research (Hauke and Kossowski, 2011). GB practices and customer behaviours were evaluated using ordinal data, specifically responses from a Likert scale that ranged from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Given that the data do not conform to

normal distribution assumptions and the anticipated relationship between the variables is both directional and monotonic, Spearman's Rank Correlation was considered suitable. This technique was employed to examine the relationships between GB practices and customers' behaviours by assessing the strength and direction of the associations between GB initiatives and customer trust, satisfaction, and loyalty. Similar methodologies have been used in previous research, where Spearman's Rank Correlation was applied to assess the associations of the independent variables on outcome measures, especially in scenarios with ordinal or non-normally distributed data (for instance, Lobo and Guntur, 2018). Among the eight item statements measuring GB practices, one statement, relating to the implementation of pro-environmental actions such as paperless transactions, resource-saving, and environmental conservation activities, was used twice to assess both customer trust and customer satisfaction.

4 Analysis

4.1 Characteristics of the respondents

The final sample consisted of 376 respondents, with a relatively balanced gender distribution (51.3% female and 48.7% male). The age distribution was concentrated in the 25–35 (34.3%) and 45–54 (30.9%) brackets, indicating most respondents are in the prime of their careers, while 18–24-year-olds made up only 14.4% and those aged 55+ just 9%, reflecting lower representation of early-career and senior age groups. A large majority (84%) held university degrees, 10.9% had professional qualifications, and small proportions had secondary education (4.3%) or technical/vocational qualifications (0.8%). Professionally, the largest group were accountants/auditors (29.3%), followed by banking executives (19.9%), with financial analysts and insurance executives both at 11.7%, and investment analysts at 8.8%. Income distribution showed that the largest single group earned Rs 20,000–39,999 (\approx USD 440–860), with substantial shares earning Rs 60,000–79,999 (\approx USD 1,320–1,760) and Rs 80,000–99,999 (\approx USD 1,760–2,200). A smaller but notable proportion (4.3%) reported incomes of Rs 100,000+ (\approx USD 2,200+), indicating a mix of mid-level and higher-earning professionals.

4.2 Customers' awareness of Green Banking

Descriptive statistics were used to assess respondents' level of GB awareness. Results from Table 3 indicate a high level of awareness and a favourable attitude toward GB. All four items recorded low mean scores ranging from 1.39 to 1.51, reflecting strong agreement overall. The strongest support was for choosing environmentally friendly banking products, such as sustainable investment funds and green savings accounts (mean = 1.39), followed by having heard of GB facilities (mean = 1.44) and awareness of GB practices like paperless transactions (mean = 1.45). Although general knowledge of GB had the highest mean (1.51), it still indicates agreement, with slightly greater variability. Standard deviations were low (0.573–0.734), suggesting consistent responses. These findings align with Sharma and Choubey (2022) who emphasised that

customer education and awareness are key drivers of positive attitudes and engagement with GB initiatives.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on Green Banking Awareness

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Heard of Green facilities (Green Loans, Green Mortgages, Green Investments) provided by banks.	1	5	1.44	0.674
Have knowledge about Green Banking.	1	5	1.51	0.734
Aware of Green Banking Practices (for example, paperless transactions) being followed by my bank.	1	5	1.45	0.668
Would consider environmentally-friendly banking products, such as sustainable investment funds or green savings accounts.	1	5	1.39	0.573

4.3 Green Banking Practices and Customer Trust

Table 4 illustrates a positive relationship between all variables. It shows that all the variables are statistically significantly correlated with each other at a positive value. For instance, the correlation coefficient of $r = 0.714$, 0.679 and 0.702 , suggest that consumers perceive banks that effectively employ technology to minimize waste as more trustworthy reliable and more secured respectively. Implementation of pro-environmental actions and using customers' investments to enhance the environment have also been found to have strong significant correlation (greater than 0.7) with the 3 dimensions of customer trust. This is in line with Malik and Singh (2022) who found that in the banking sector, the application of technologies focused on enhancing resource and energy efficiency reassures customers about the reliability and sustainability of environmentally friendly financial institutions. This concludes that Green Banking has a positive association with Customer Trust.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix between items of GB Practices and Customer Trust

Green Banking Practices	Customer Trust		
	Can trust banks which engage in GB.	Believe that banks engaged in GB are generally reliable.	Feel secure to be involved with banks which practice GB.
Implement pro-environmental actions such as paperless transactions, resource-saving, and environmental conservation activities.	.836** .000	.805** .000	.828** .000
Relies on technology to avoid wasting resources.	.714** .000	.679** .000	.702** .000
Using customers' deposits or investments to enhance the environmental and living conditions of society.	.706** .000	.742** .000	.719** .000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) (n = 376)

4.4 Green Banking on Customer Satisfaction

The Spearman's rho correlations highlight strong relationships between various GB initiatives and customer satisfaction. In particular, the significantly high correlations at $r = 0.897$, 0.906 and 0.884 , show that when banks implement pro-environmental actions such as paperless transactions, resource-saving, and environmental conservation activities, customers feel satisfied and proud with the feeling of having taken the right decision to associate themselves with the bank. Furthermore, strong environmental commitments and effectively communicating on them contribute to the satisfaction level as indicated by significant positive correlations coefficients of magnitude above 0.65. This aligns with the findings of Nair and Gopakumar (2017), who found a positive correlation between GB initiatives and customer satisfaction of banking customers across various regions of India. Therefore, it can be concluded that GB has a positive significant association with Customer Satisfaction.

Table 5: Correlation Matrix between GB Practices and Customer Satisfaction

Green Banking Practices	Customer Satisfaction		
	Satisfied when my bank offers a broad range of green products.	Feel proud when my bank has a green corporate image.	It is the right decision to be a customer of banks which are engaged in green practices.
Implement pro-environmental actions such as paperless transactions, resource-saving, and environmental conservation activities.	.897** .000	.906** .000	.884** .000
Effectively communicate their green initiatives.	.678** .000	.706** .000	.704** .000
Strong environmental commitments.	.689** .000	.698** .000	.709** .000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) (n = 376)

4.5 Green Banking on Customer Loyalty

Table 6 clearly shows that there is a significant positive correlation among the items of the variables. Specifically, green mortgages show strong positive correlations with customers' intention to continue dealing with environmentally responsible banks ($r = 0.695$), remain loyal ($r = 0.658$), and recommend such banks to others ($r = 0.662$). Similarly, green loans/green financing exhibit strong correlations with continuing patronage ($r = 0.701$), loyalty ($r = 0.681$), and recommendation intentions ($r = 0.666$). Notably, the practice of promoting the development of a green environment for customers demonstrates an exceptionally strong correlation with customers' intention to continue dealing with the bank ($r = 0.944$), and strong correlations with loyalty ($r = 0.675$) and word-of-mouth recommendation ($r = 0.687$). This aligns with the findings of Ibe-enwo, Igbudu, Garanti, and Popoola (2019), whose survey on retail banking customers in North Cyprus showed that GB practices directly and positively influence customer loyalty.

Table 6: Correlation Matrix between GB Practices and Customer Loyalty

Green Banking Practices	Customer Loyalty		
	Continue to deal with banks that prioritize environmental concerns.	Remain loyal to banks which are environmentally responsible.	Recommend banks with green practices to my acquaintances.
Green mortgages – better interest rates and conditions for energy-efficient houses or buildings.	.695** .000	.658** .000	.662** .000
Green loans/ green financing - special attention to energy efficient projects, promote renewable energy.	.701** .000	.681** .000	.666** .000
Promotes the development of a green environment for customers.	.944** .000	.675** .000	.687** .000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) (n = 376)

5 Discussion and Conclusion

The research shows that GB in Mauritius has a positive association with customers' behaviours, particularly Customer Trust, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. GB shows a positive association with customer trust as consumers perceive banks that effectively employ technology to minimize waste as more trustworthy. This is because when banks adopt measures like going paperless, offering digital statements, operating in an energy-efficient manner, and engaging in eco-friendly financing, customers often perceive these actions as indicators that the bank is responsible, open, and forward-thinking. GB shows a positive association with customer satisfaction as when customers perceive a bank as having strong environmental commitments, they are more likely to feel satisfied in choosing that bank. GB practices such as online banking, mobile applications, electronic statements, and cashless transactions enhance customer satisfaction by providing environmental advantages along with increased convenience, efficiency, and accessibility. This blend of ethical and practical benefits enables banks to align with customers' financial and lifestyle aspirations. GB also shows a positive association with customer loyalty indicating that as banks promote green environments, customers are more likely to recommend the bank to others, highlighting the role of environmental initiatives in driving customer advocacy. For the banking industry in Mauritius, these insights are particularly important. As the financial sector in the country evolves, the leading banking institutions in Mauritius are ideally positioned to take

advantage of GB initiatives to enhance both operational effectiveness and customer relationships. The findings indicated that the potential of GB initiatives not only promotes sustainable development but also strengthens customer connections. By recognizing and addressing the changing demands of eco-conscious consumers, banks can build customer trust and encourage lasting loyalty. Additionally, this insight provides bank leaders and decision-makers with the ability to make strategic investments focused on sustainability that enhance both environmental outcomes and financial success. Over time, these eco-friendly initiatives could influence how banks are valued and viewed within the economy, reinforcing their dedication to responsible and progressive banking practices.

Nevertheless, the results provide a helpful starting point for further research by pointing out noteworthy trends and connections that demand more investigation. The study provides preliminary empirical insights that advance our knowledge of the topic and suggest possible directions for further confirmatory research.

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